

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT, COSTS ON INNOVATION AND THE ECONOMY'S DIGITAL: RESULTS OF MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a several researches carried out in order to reveal the relationship between the business environment, costs on innovation and the economy's digital. A multivariate grouping of countries was carried out according to digital cost, outcome estimates and business environment characteristics using the cluster analysis tool. In addition, regression analysis was used to assess the influence of cost and quality characteristics of digitalization on the indicator of digitalization readiness both in general and by individual groups of countries.

Keywords: business environment, costs on innovation, digitalization readiness, cluster analysis, regression analysis.

In recent years, a new wave of business model transformation has spread due to the emergence of a new generation of digital technologies: artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, wireless communication technologies, etc. The topic of digitalization of business processes is becoming more and more relevant in the strategic development agenda of enterprises. Currently, digital transformation is an important tool to ensure the sustainable development of enterprises in conditions of uncertainty, to reduce the costs of developing new products and the time to bring them to the market, to introduce modern approaches to the formation of new qualities and to meet the trends of scientific and technological development. From this point of view, it is of great analytical interest to assess the impact of digital costs, quantitative and qualitative characteristics on the development of the digital economy.

The purpose of this research is to reveal the relationship between cost, outcome estimates and business environment characteristics of the digital sector. Several studies have been conducted to achieve this goal. A number of indicators were used in the studies, which were selected in terms of belonging to one of the following three groups:

1. cost indicators of innovations, digital (relative or absolute amounts of costs),
2. business environment characteristics,
3. result indicators characterizing the state of digital.

Table 1 describes the indicators used in the research. First of all, the letter designations of these indicators in the models and analyzes are indicated, followed by their full name, as well as the source of the indicator in the form of a reference.

Table 1.

Indicators used in research

Letter designation	Full name
E_Gov_Ind	E-Government Index [4]
E_Part_Ind	E-Participation Index [4]
Online_Service_Ind	Online Service Index [4]
HDI	Human Capital Index [4]
Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	Telecommunication Infrastructure Index [4]
DRI	Digital Readiness Index [2]
Ease_of_DB	Ease of Doing Business [2]
GII	Global Innovation Index [3]
Instit_1	Institutions [3]
Business_envir_1_3	Business environment [3]
Infr_3	Infrastructure [3]
Business_soph_5	Business sophistication [3]
Exp_on_educ_2_2_1	Expenditure on education, % GDP [3]
Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2	Gross expenditure on R&D (GERD) [3]
Exp_by_business_5_1_3	GERD performed by business enterprise [3]
Exp_fin_by_business_5_1_4	GERD financed by business enterprise [3]

Research 1.

In this part of the study, we tried to identify the relationship between the cost and outcome estimates of the digitalization sector. For this purpose, we have carried out a multivariate grouping of countries according to the cost characteristics and the outcome estimates of the digital sector, using the cluster analysis tool [1]. As cost characteristics, we considered the share of Expenditure on education in GDP, Gross expenditure on R&D (GERD), as well as the GERD on R&D financed by the business enterprise. And as the outcome characteristics of the digital sphere, we considered the most

general assessments of the digital sphere: Digital Readiness Index, E-Government Index and Telecommunication Infrastructure Index.

The objects of research are 127 countries with different levels of development.

As a result of the analysis, 5 clusters were distinguished, of which 26 countries were included in the first cluster, 28 countries in the second cluster, 14 countries in the third cluster, 7 countries in the fourth cluster, and 52 countries in the fifth cluster.

Table 2 shows the membership of the clusters according to the countries considered, and Table 3 summarizes the final centers of the clusters according to the indicators used for clustering.

Table 2.

Cluster Membership					
Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5	
Azerbaijan	Austria	Argentina	China	Albania	Mauritius
Belarus	Belgium	Armenia	Germany	Algeria	Mongolia
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Brazil	Botswana	Japan	Australia	Mozambique
Bulgaria	Colombia	Burkina Faso	Republic of Korea	Bangladesh	Myanmar
Canada	Denmark	Cambodia	Switzerland	Benin	Nepal
Chile	Finland	Guatemala	Thailand	Bolivia	Niger
Croatia	France	Honduras	United Arab Emirates	Cameroon	Nigeria
Cyprus	Hungary	Latvia		Côte d'Ivoire	Pakistan
Czech Republic	Ireland	Mexico		Costa Rica	Panama
El Salvador	Italy	Montenegro		Dominican Republic	Paraguay
Estonia	Kazakhstan	Namibia		Ecuador	Peru
Greece	Luxembourg	Republic of Moldova		Egypt	Qatar
Iceland	Malaysia	Serbia		Ethiopia	Rwanda
India	Malta	Tunisia		Georgia (Country)	Saudi Arabia
Israel	Netherlands			Ghana	Senegal
Lithuania	New Zealand			Guinea	Tajikistan
Morocco	Poland			Indonesia	Togo
North Macedonia	Portugal			Iran (Islamic Republic of)	Trinidad and Tobago
Norway	Romania			Jamaica	Uganda
Oman	Singapore			Jordan	United Republic of Tanzania
Philippines	Slovakia			Kenya	Uruguay
Russian Federation	Slovenia			Kuwait	Yemen
South Africa	Spain			Kyrgyzstan	Zambia
Sri Lanka	Sweden			Lao People's Democratic Republic	Zimbabwe
Ukraine	Turkey			Lebanon	
Uzbekistan	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland			Madagascar	
	United States of America			Malawi	
	Viet Nam			Mali	

Table 3.

	Cluster				
	1	2	3	4	5
DRI	.46	1.02	-.11	1.12	-.52
Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	.71	.82	.58	.87	.46
E_Gov_Ind	.76	.85	.63	.86	.54
Exp_on_educ_2_2_1	4.47	4.78	4.54	3.11	3.36
Exp_fin_by_business_5_1_4	36.28	53.85	15.70	74.60	1.59
Gross_Expnd_om_RD_2_3_2	.94	1.60	.39	2.67	.27

From the analysis of the results, it becomes clear that the countries are significantly different in terms of both expenditure (especially according to the GERD financed by business enterprise) and output characteristics. Thus, the group of countries with the lowest evaluations in terms of all expenditure indicators also recorded the lowest level in the outcome estimates of the digital sector.

By the same logic, the group of countries that recorded the highest results with almost all spending characteristics also recorded the highest results with Digital Readiness Index, E-Government Index and Telecommunication Infrastructure Index.

From the results, it can be concluded that those countries that direct significant funds to the development of the education, R&D sector, both by the public and private sectors, record a high result in improving the general indicators of the digital sector.

It should be noted that the largest number of countries are in the group of countries with the lowest results in almost all indicators.

From the analysis of the membership of the clusters, it can be noticed that the countries with a relatively high level of socio-economic development, which allocate large funds to the development of innovation and education, are among the groups of countries that recorded the highest results in terms of the characteristics of the digitalization sector. Meanwhile, countries with weakly developed economies, which allocate little funds for the development of the digital sector, and

therefore have the least opportunities to develop the sector, recorded a low result of the general assessments of the digital sector.

It should be noted that Armenia is in the third group of countries, which is notable for its relatively low level of cost characteristics and network readiness. It is worth noting the fact that although Armenia surpasses the group average in the general assessments of the digital sector, it is still below the group average in two of the cost assessments, in particular, in terms of the share of Expenditure on education in GDP, Gross expenditure on R&D.

Research 2.

In this part of the study, 127 countries were grouped according to business environment and digital performance scores. Indicators of ease of doing business and business sophistication were considered as characteristics of the business environment. Here, too, Digital Readiness Index, E-Government Index and Telecommunication Infrastructure Index were identified as the outcome characteristics of the digital sector.

As a result of the analysis, 5 clusters were distinguished, of which 26 countries were included in the first cluster, 31 countries in the second cluster, 43 countries in the third cluster, 10 countries in the fourth cluster, and 17 countries in the fifth cluster.

Table 4 shows the membership of the clusters according to the countries considered, and Table 5 summarizes the final centers of the clusters according to the indicators used for clustering.

Table 4.

Cluster Membership					
Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3		Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Brazil	Algeria	Albania	North Macedonia	Finland	Australia
Bulgaria	Bangladesh	Argentina	Oman	Israel	Austria
Canada	Benin	Armenia	Pakistan	Japan	Belgium
China	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Azerbaijan	Paraguay	Luxembourg	Cameroon
Colombia	Burkina Faso	Belarus	Qatar	Netherlands	Chile
Estonia	Cambodia	Bolivia	Republic of Moldova	Republic of Korea	Cyprus
Hungary	Costa Rica	Botswana	Rwanda	Singapore	Czech Republic
India	Egypt	Côte d'Ivoire	Serbia	Sweden	Denmark
Italy	Ethiopia	Croatia	Sri Lanka	Switzerland	France
Latvia	Ghana	Dominican Republic	Turkey	United States of America	Germany
Lithuania	Indonesia	Ecuador	Uruguay		Iceland
Malaysia	Iran (Islamic Republic of)	El Salvador	Zambia		Ireland
New Zealand	Kyrgyzstan	Georgia (Country)			Malta
Peru	Madagascar	Greece			Norway
Philippines	Mali	Guatemala			Slovenia
Poland	Mauritius	Guinea			United Arab Emirates
Portugal	Morocco	Honduras			United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
Romania	Mozambique	Jamaica			
Russian Federation	Myanmar	Jordan			
Saudi Arabia	Namibia	Kazakhstan			
Slovakia	Panama	Kenya			
South Africa	Senegal	Kuwait			
Spain	Tajikistan	Lao People's Democratic Republic			
Thailand	Togo	Lebanon			
Ukraine	Trinidad and Tobago	Malawi			
Viet Nam	Tunisia	Mexico			
	Uganda	Mongolia			
	United Republic of Tanzania	Montenegro			
	Uzbekistan	Nepal			
	Yemen	Niger			
	Zimbabwe	Nigeria			

Table 5.

	Final Cluster Centers				
	Cluster				
	1	2	3	4	5
Ease_of_DB	.40	-.54	.00	1.29	.98
DRI	.45	-.65	-.20	1.78	1.11
E_Gov_Ind	.78	.52	.61	.91	.85
Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	.73	.44	.54	.92	.84
Business_soph_5	33.68	17.06	23.68	61.90	49.47

The results of the cluster analysis show that the differences are significant for all indicators.

It is noteworthy that the picture is consistent with both the characteristics of the business environment and the general indicators of digital. Thus, the group of countries with the highest score in terms of business environment evaluations stands out for its high level of digital readiness, e-government development and telecommunication infrastructure indicators. By the same logic, the group of countries that recorded the lowest result of the indicator of ease of doing business and business sophistication is also characterized by the lowest level of general assessments of digitalization.

From the analysis of the membership of the clusters, it can be noticed that the countries with a high level of development of the business environment and significant results in the development of the digitalization sector are in the cluster with the highest results. On the contrary, in the group of countries with the lowest characteristics, there are countries with a low level of socio-

economic development, where there is a need for large-scale transformations aimed at improving the business environment and development in the field of digitalization.

It should be noted that within the framework of the analysis, Armenia appeared in the third cluster, which is the group of countries with the second worst results. It is noteworthy that Armenia exceeds the group average in terms of all indicators.

Research 3.

In this part of the study, we carried out a multivariate regression analysis of the existing general assessment of the digital sector and the impact of quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the sector [1]. The Digital Readiness Index from the general assessments of the digitalization industry was considered as a dependent variable, and the Gross expenditure on R&D, Business sophistication, Telecommunication Infrastructure Index and Institutions were considered as independent variables.

Table 6.

Results of regression analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.956 ^a	.914	.911	.27456

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Instit_1, Business_soph_5

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	97.228	4	24.307	322.454	.000 ^b
	Residual	9.197	122	.075		
	Total	106.424	126			

a. Dependent Variable: DRI
b. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Instit_1, Business_soph_5

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-2.639	.141		-18.649	.000
	Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	2.325	.178	.584	13.072	.000
	Instit_1	.013	.003	.201	3.951	.000
	Business_soph_5	.017	.003	.252	4.881	.000
	Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2	.002	.044	.002	.051	.960

a. Dependent Variable: DRI

From the results of the regression analysis, it becomes obvious that the influence of telecommunication infrastructure, quality of institutions and business sophistication assessments had the most significant impact on the improvement of the digital readiness in the observed countries. It is noteworthy that the Gross expenditure on R&D has a low significance.

In total, the above four assessments together explain about 91 percent of the variation in the Digital Readiness Index.

It should be noted that by placing the relevant indicators of Armenia within the framework of the obtained regression model, we will get the value of the digital readiness indicator of 0.13, while the actual value of the Digital Readiness Index for Armenia exceeds it (0.16), which indicates a high level of potential assimilation.

It is also interesting to reveal the relationship between the Global Innovation Index and the characteristics of the business environment.

Table 7.

Results of regression analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.925 ^a	.856	.853	4.77327
a. Predictors: (Constant), Business_soph_5, Business_envir_1_3, Ease_of_DB				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16678.141	3	5559.380	244.002	.000 ^b
	Residual	2802.448	123	22.784		
	Total	19480.589	126			
a. Dependent Variable: GII						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Business_soph_5, Business_envir_1_3, Ease_of_DB						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.511	3.195		2.038	.044
	Ease_of_DB	4.611	.721	.316	6.392	.000
	Business_envir_1_3	.158	.050	.154	3.187	.002
	Business_soph_5	.502	.044	.567	11.496	.000
a. Dependent Variable: GII						

From the results of the regression analysis, it is clear that there is a significant relationship between the Global Innovation Index and the business environment, ease of doing business, and business sophistication ratings. Moreover, the above three characteristics of the business environment together explain about 85 percent of the variation in the Global Innovation Index.

The obtained results prove that the measures aimed at improving the business environment had a significant impact on increasing the level of global innovation.

Applying the obtained regression model, we will get the Global Innovation Index value of 31.9 for Armenia, which is close to the actual value of Armenia according to the Global Innovation Index (32.6).

Research 4.

In this part of the study, we grouped countries by the Digital Readiness Index, according to which the following groups were distinguished:

1. up to -0.25 (43 countries)
2. from -0.24 to 0.42 (42 countries)
3. above 0.43 (42 countries).

Then, for each of the groups, a multivariate regression analysis was carried out to reveal the influence of the cost and quality characteristics of digitization (the Gross expenditure on R&D, business sophistication, quality assessments of institutions and infrastructure) on the Digital Readiness Index.

Let's present the results of multivariate regression analysis by individual groups.

1. Up to -0.25 (43 countries)

Table 8.

Results of regression analysis

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.791 ^a	.625	.586	.23734		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Business_soph_5, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Instit_1						
ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	3.569	4	.892	15.839	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.140	38	.056		
	Total	5.709	42			
a. Dependent Variable: DRI						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Business_soph_5, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Instit_1						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.225	.250		-4.895	.000
	Instit_1	-.011	.005	-.260	-2.407	.021
	Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	1.700	.244	.716	6.981	.000
	Business_soph_5	.013	.006	.239	2.372	.023
	Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2	.308	.157	.215	1.961	.057
a. Dependent Variable: DRI						

From the results of the multivariate regression analysis conducted for this group, it can be seen that both the improvement of the quality of institutions and infrastructures, as well as the increase of the index of business sophistication and the Gross expenditure on

R&D are significant for increasing the level of digital readiness in the countries of this group. In total, the above four assessments together explain about 59 percent of the variation in the Digital Readiness Index.

2. From -0.24 to 0.42 (42 countries)

Table 9.

Results of regression analysis

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.805 ^a	.647	.609	.12279		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Instit_1, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Business_soph_5						
ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1.024	4	.256	16.977	.000 ^b
	Residual	.558	37	.015		
	Total	1.582	41			
a. Dependent Variable: DRI						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Instit_1, Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Business_soph_5						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.493	.252		-5.921	.000
	Instit_1	.008	.004	.235	2.307	.027
	Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	1.574	.234	.734	6.731	.000
	Business_soph_5	.002	.004	.071	.588	.560
	Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2	-.030	.051	-.072	-5.86	.562
a. Dependent Variable: DRI						

The obtained results show that the cost and quality characteristics of digitization together explain about 61 percent of the variation in the Digital Readiness Index of this group of countries.

3. Above 0.43 (42 countries)

It is worth paying attention to the fact that the improvement of indicators of business sophistication and the Gross expenditure on R&D are not significant factors for increasing the level of digital readiness.

Table 10.

Results of regression analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.886 ^a	.785	.761	.26210

a. Predictors: (Constant), Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Instit_1, Business_soph_5

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.259	4	2.315	33.697	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.542	37	.069		
	Total	11.801	41			

a. Dependent Variable: DRI
b. Predictors: (Constant), Telecommunic_Infr_Ind, Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2, Instit_1, Business_soph_5

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.263	.621		-6.869	.000
	Instit_1	.031	.007	.436	4.290	.000
	Business_soph_5	.010	.006	.232	1.735	.091
	Gross_Expend_om_RD_2_3_2	-.046	.054	-.095	-.845	.403
	Telecommunic_Infr_Ind	3.042	.755	.424	4.028	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DRI

From the results of the multivariate regression analysis for the group of countries with the highest result, it is clear that compared to the other two groups, the considered dependent variables together explain a greater part of the variation in the Digital Readiness Index (76 percent).

It is noteworthy that for this group of countries, the increase in the Gross expenditure on R&D is not a significant factor in increasing the level of the Digital Readiness Index. In this context, referring to the results recorded in the previous two groups, we can state that along with the increase in digital readiness, the increase in the Gross expenditure on R&D is not a significant factor affecting the level of the Digital Readiness Index.

It should be noted that Armenia is in the second group of countries in the level of digitization readiness. In order to find out how much Armenia uses its potential compared to the average of the group, we put Armenia's indicators in the regression equation obtained for that group. As a result, a value of 0.09 for the Digital Readiness Index was obtained for Armenia. Taking into account that the actual value of the Digital Readiness Index for Armenia was 0.16, it can be stated

that Armenia used its potential better than the average of the group.

Thus, the conducted researches made it possible to reveal the relationship between the cost and result estimates of the digital sector and the characteristics of the business environment. In addition, the performed regression analyzes made it possible to assess the influence of the cost and quality characteristics of digitization on the Digital Readiness Index both in general and by individual groups of countries.

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